

A REVIEW OF INDICATORS AND SENSOR TECHNOLOGIES TO ASSESS PIG WELFARE AT THE SLAUGHTERHOUSE

Ramon-Perez¹, Angela; Forkman², Björn; Manteca¹, Xavier; Llonch¹, Pol

¹ Department of Animal and Food Science, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Campus UAB, 08139 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Bellaterra), Barcelona, Spain

² Section of Animal Welfare and Disease Control, Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Groennegaardsvej 8, 1870 Frederiksberg C, Denmark

angela.ramon@uab.cat

Pigs, as any other meat-producing animals, end their lives at the slaughterhouse. The abattoir represents a crucial place for the collection of numerous data relating to a large number of animals, including their welfare status. A systematic review following PRISMA guidelines was conducted to identify studies using animal-based and resource-based indicators to assess pig welfare (including farm, transport, and slaughterhouse) in three literature search engines. Once the relevant indicators and methodologies for assessing pig welfare at the slaughterhouse were obtained, a commercial search was performed to identify technological solutions capable of evaluating these indicators. A total of 1583 papers were initially identified, selecting 119 for analysis, resulting in 57 specific studies focusing on assessment at the slaughterhouse. Fifty-three different welfare indicators were identified, including 16 related to on-farm welfare issues and 37 related to welfare during transport or at slaughterhouse. Twenty-eight *antemortem* indicators were found, for assessing consciousness after stunning ($n=9$), handling stress ($n=6$), heat stress ($n=4$), restricted movement ($n=3$), undefined stress ($n=2$), prolonged thirst ($n=1$), group stress ($n=1$), gastro-enteric disorders ($n=1$), and locomotor disorder ($n=1$). The remaining 25 indicators were to be performed *postmortem*, monitoring undefined stress ($n=8$), gastro-enteric disorders ($n=2$), respiratory disorders ($n=4$), soft tissue lesions and integument damage ($n=5$), other disorders ($n=3$), restricted movement ($n=1$), prolonged hunger ($n=1$), and muscle exhaustion ($n=1$). Most of these indicators were assessed by a human observer ($n=40$), while a small group of biomarkers were required to be analysed at the laboratory ($n=9$), and a few were evaluated by sensors such as computer vision ($n=2$) and infrared cameras ($n=1$). It should be noted that 12 indicators which were assessed by a human observer were also evaluated by using image analysis technologies. From the commercial search, two different computer vision technologies located at the slaughter line were found, one for assessing tail lesions and length, and another for assessing signs of pneumonia and pleurisy in the lungs. Additionally, two prototype technologies were found, one computer vision camera for automatically assessing consciousness after stunning using corneal reflex, and another for monitoring bleeding through thermal image analysis. This review provides a detailed description of the state of the art in assessing pig welfare at the slaughterhouse and elucidates the potential for sensors to enhance the welfare assessment.